

Fig. 1. Result of MPI Communication Microbenchmark with message size equal to, 0.1x size of, and 3.0x size of what our application uses during communication in our paper.

For running the microbenchmark, we consider two different HPC nodes which try to send a message to each other via `MPI_Isend`. The `MPI_Wait` is then used to ensure the completion of the communication. We perform local computations while messages are moving. The local computation time is varied to see the effect of the overlapping communication with computation.

We run the microbenchmark for three message sizes:

- Message that has size equal to what our application uses (1.0x Message Size).
- Message that has size 0.1x of what our application uses (0.1x Message Size).
- Message that has size 3x of what our application uses (3.0x Message Size).

Results shown in Figure 1 indicates that if local compute time is large enough, communication can be hidden when asynchronous message progression is activated for Intel MPI. Further observation is as follows.

- OpenMPI: messages are progressed after `MPI_Wait` is called, resulting in non-overlap of communication and computation. Communication time is constant throughout, and total time increases linearly with the local compute time.
- Intel MPI: when the local compute time is small (less than 1ms for our example), total time depends solely on communication. For larger compute times, communication is completely hidden, resulting in identical values for compute time and total time (perfect overlap).

We exhausted our allocation on IBM POWER9 cluster and thus we had to run the microbenchmark on available Intel cluster. We compare OpenMPI and Intel MPI in Intel-based cluster with Infiniband. We expect the result of OpenMPI should be representative if we run the microbenchmark on IBM POWER9 cluster.

It is explicitly stated that Intel MPI support asynchronous progression¹, whereas we do not see the same thing for OpenMPI. This is also consistent with our observations: perfect overlap between computation and communication for Intel MPI, but not for OpenMPI. We also tried to forcefully move the messages by using `MPI_Test` and `MPI_Probe`, but they did not help.

¹<https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/develop/documentation/mpi-developer-guide-linux/top/additional-supported-features/asynchronous-progress-control.html>